

**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

D5.1 Results of Landscape Mapping

Overview Report

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1. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of WP5 - Policy, as set out in the SIC grant agreement, is to increase understanding about how social innovation can contribute to meeting the policy objectives of the European Union and its Member States, and increase the relevance and effectiveness of public policy related to social innovation. The WP's specific objectives are:

- 01** To increase policymakers' awareness, understanding and uptake of effective public policy approaches to support social innovation and build skills and capacity of social innovation networks to engage more effectively with policymakers;
- 02** To advocate for policy change in key areas that will enable social innovation to be better supported, within and across member states;
- 03** To regularly review the impact of social innovation on meeting EU policy objectives, providing clear evidence and recommendations on how greater impact can be achieved.

Aims of T5.1

Task 5.1, 'Situational Analysis', was a stocktaking exercise to explore the interaction of public policy (particularly at an EU level) and social innovation to date, and to set the groundwork for subsequent tasks in WP5. Our intention was to review reports and other materials produced to date, relevant to social innovation policy at a general level and specific to the different SIC networks, and to synthesise findings into concise outputs that would be accessible to policymakers and social innovation practitioners which could be widely disseminated. Specifically, the task aimed to:

- 01** Get a good understanding of current state of play regarding EU policy relevant to SI generally, and SIC's networks
- 02** Identify gaps, issues, tensions, policy challenges etc. that might form priorities for future WP5 Policy tasks (e.g. identifying where to target our future activities in order to make most impact)
- 03** Inform design of later WP5 Policy tasks
- 04** Generate findings and content to feed into first 'state of the union' report (T5.3)

2. METHODOLOGY

In consultation with the other seven SIC partners involved in WP5, task leaders Nesta developed a template for conducting the policy review/situational analysis. The template prompted partners to assess and understand policy needs, opportunities, tensions and gaps, and to highlight good policy examples related to:

- 01** The SIC networks that partners are facilitating
- 02** Broader policy to support social innovation at a European level (including EC-funded social innovation programmes)
- 03** National/regional policy frameworks relating to social innovation network focuses or social innovation at a broader level

Where partners were facilitating an SIC network, they were asked to focus on this network in conducting the review. Partners who were not facilitating SIC networks were asked to take a broader view of social innovation policy at an EU level. Each partner was also asked to research and create a rough draft of two national or regional examples of social innovation policy.

Partners completed the templates and returned them to the task leader. Each was then peer reviewed by another WP partner. The completed templates were not intended to be written up as publishable prose, or even to include a significant level of analysis; the aim was instead to use them as a data gathering tool, clearly sourced and referenced, so that future WP5 activities (including, in particular, the preparation of D5.3, the first 'state of the union' report) could easily draw on this initial scan and re-purpose the findings, potentially for a range of different outputs.

Nesta also conducted meetings with EC staff from DG-RTD, DG-REGIO, DG-GROW and JRC in order to explore EC policymakers' interests and needs, to inform the design and focus of outputs.

3. RESULTS AND OUTPUTS

The stocktaking exercise showed that in practice, there is considerable variation in the extent to which different SIC networks have expressed 'policy needs' to date. In some areas, for example public sector innovation, the social economy and digital social innovation, where existing networks are well established and/or mapping and policy work has already been funded by the EC, policy 'needs' are fairly well established and clear 'policy asks' have often

been formulated. In other areas where networks are only just starting to emerge and formalise, such as inclusive development, there are fewer examples of policy needs/asks clearly related to that specific network. At the same time, the review suggested that the types of policies that support or inhibit social innovation are similar across many of the network areas, even while some networks (like digital social innovation) also have some distinctive needs.

T5.1 was useful in informing WP5's ongoing strategy. Rather directing future tasks to policy analysis (such as benchmarking the state of social innovation policy across a number of EU countries), the review suggested that partners' time over the remainder of the project will be most effectively used by focusing on changing the ways that policymakers and social innovation practitioners work together. The landscape mapping highlighted new policy models or approaches, such as public sector hackathons and problem-based procurement, which point to the value of policymakers and social innovation practitioners working together in new ways. In synthesising the findings, this led to the development of a theoretical framework - 'policies *for* and *as* social innovation' - which unpacked the role policymakers could play, not just supporting social innovation through relevant policy instruments, but also by leveraging social innovation approaches. Examples of the latter include taking a more human-centred design approach to incorporate user insights in the policy development process, or building partnerships with practitioners to address particular policy challenges (as is the case with Mobilearn in Sweden).

This has informed the development of subsequent deliverables in WP5. The first 'state of the union' report (D5.3), for example, will take a more practice-oriented approach by introducing policymakers to a range of 'principles for socially innovative policy'. T5.4, the 'policy master classes', which were first envisaged more as 'training' sessions, will now be designed as collaborative workshops that support policymakers to work with social innovators in tackling public policy challenges. Over the series of workshops, we will develop and refine the workshop format (based around the 'seven principles of socially innovative policymaking'), along with tools and prompt sheets to run sessions within these workshops, which will later be codified so that they can be used by others. This workshop format and accompanying tools will in turn form a resource for the Policy Portal (T5.5), which will sit within Learning Repository being developed in WP4.

Description of D5.1 outputs

Based on the materials gathered through Task 5.1 and the insights from policymakers and partners, eight short documents were produced. These aim to synthesise findings from the

situational analysis in a simple and engaging way, and form the first of a series of policy-related outputs to be produced over the course of the SIC project. They include three documents that set out the idea of policy as/for social innovation, four case study examples (one in the form of an interview), and one tool for policymakers to use:

- 01 Introducing the SIC policy framework: Policies for/as social innovation (Graphic)** Based on the insights gathered as part of T5.1, this designed output visually describes the relationship of policymaking for social innovation and policymaking as a socially innovative process.
- 02 Policy for social innovation: Five ways policy can support social innovation** (short briefing paper).
- 03 The Seven Principles of Socially Innovative Policymaking** (short briefing paper).
- 04 Policy prompt sheet:** applying the seven principles of social innovation to policy (Worksheet).
- 05 Regional example 1:** 'Community Lab, Emilia Romagna Region: Using openness and collaboration to better respond to complex social challenges'.
- 06 Regional example 2:** 'La 27e Région works with policymakers to create a culture that supports social innovation in French regional government'.
- 07 Regional example 3:** 'e-Estonia: how Estonia's national digital strategy could open up more opportunities for digital social innovation in the region'.
- 08 Interview:** Mobilearn – the digital platform supporting migrant integration.

4. DISSEMINATION AND NEXT STEPS

The outputs developed as part of the D5.1 Landscape Mapping exercise have been used to develop a series of policy outputs which can be practically useful to three broad audience groups: 1) Those who are new to social innovation policy, from any sector/role; 2) Social innovation practitioners (this will include but is not limited to network actors) who could work with policymakers to help achieve policy objectives; and 3) Policymakers/ public decisionmakers who could benefit from understanding how they can better support social innovation or make better use of social innovation policy principles.

As part of their ongoing network engagement activities, WP partners, particularly network facilitators, have been requested to continue developing content (e.g. blogs, interviews) which illustrates the value of social innovators creating effective partnerships with policymakers and public authorities to make change, and there will be a consortium-wide effort to continually update the Policy Portal (T5.5) with engaging and up-to-date content.

To support the dissemination of these and later multimedia outputs, WP leaders Nesta are devising a dissemination plan to engage with policymakers across Europe who could make use of these outputs. Nesta has already taken first steps towards engaging with different stakeholder groups, such as:

- 01** Exploring opportunities to integrate aspects of the social innovation policy principles into the Royal College of Art's Design for Policy modules (London, UK)
- 02** Held a meeting with DG REGIO and agreed to circulate D5.1 outputs to INTERREG national points of contact, to introduce them to the work and invite them to share social innovation policy success stories via the SIC website
- 03** Promoting D5.1 outputs through related social marketing channels: e.g. the public sector innovation newsletter – Lab Notes; a partnership between Nesta (UK) , SIX (UK), MindLab (Denmark), MaRS Solutions Lab (Canada), and GovLab (US); Linking to the content from the Design For Europe website and encouraging partners to help promote the content from their organisations' social media accounts

Social innovation and policymaking

Public policy can both support social innovation, and be socially innovative in itself

Social innovation is about developing and implementing new ideas to meet social needs and create new social relationships. Social innovations can take many forms - from products and services (like Mobilelearn), to institutions (like government innovation lab La 27e Région), initiatives (like the White House's Call to Action campaign) and ways of doing things (such as the Behavioural Insights Team's EAST model to help policymakers apply behavioural insights to the policy process).

We often say that social innovation is 'social in means and ends' - the innovation process benefits people, as well as the outcome. For example, social innovation may involve: Changing power relations; Improving human capabilities; Inviting input from a wide range of people; Blurring boundaries between public, private and civil society sectors; Redistributing wealth and assets.

POLICY FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION

Public policy can support social innovation by using a number of policy levers to stimulate supply and demand for it and creating an environment where social innovations can thrive. We call this **policy**

POLICY AS SOCIAL INNOVATION

Policymakers can be social innovators too, using social innovation principles in the way they design new policies, programmes and initiatives to:

- Rethink how policy challenges are approached and framed
- Open the policy process up to different ideas and perspectives
- Make use of human-centred design approaches
- Collaborate with citizens, users and other stakeholders
- Design policy solutions that are experimental and seek to make better use of evidence
- Develop policy in a more iterative way
- Make connections to other initiatives and search for ways to scale impact

Over the course of the Social Innovation Community project, we will be leading a series of practical workshops intended to highlight the different ways in which policymakers can support social innovation. Further, as part of this work, Social Innovation Community will set out to equip policymakers with the insights and tools needed to apply socially innovative approaches to real policy challenges, in order to help create a sharing, learning community of socially innovative policymakers in Europe.

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Get in touch : Twitter @SICommunity_EU hashtag #socinnpolicy

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**SOCIAL
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Policy for social innovation

Five ways policy can support social
innovation

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693883.

Policy for social innovation

Five ways policy can support social innovation

To start the Social Innovation Community project we reviewed what social innovators and researchers have said so far about the relationship between public policy and social innovation.

Across Europe there are many initiatives operating nationally and transnationally that have been designed to support social innovation, but we're still some way from a well-developed field of 'social innovation policy'. Nevertheless, from this work so far we can start to sketch out what this might look like.

Public policy can both **enhance supply of and demand for social innovation**, as well as creating a **wider environment** in which social innovations can thrive. Picking up on each of these objectives, here are five areas of activity where public policymakers have a clear role to play in supporting social innovation.

1. FUNDING FOR EARLY-STAGE INITIATIVES, SCALE-UPS AND INTERMEDIARIES

Unsurprisingly, funding tops the list of needs for many social innovators, including grants (widely seen as important for early-stage seed funding) and investment. Policymakers at both European and national government level have prioritised this issue. EC actions have included the [Social Business Initiative](#) to support social enterprise, and greater prioritisation of social innovation within structural funds. It has also invested in intermediaries to support social innovators - like incubators and accelerators - through the [TRANSITION](#) and [BENISI](#) projects.

At a national level, there have been a number of innovations in the last few years. The UK government, for example, set out a strategy for [growing the social investment market](#) in 2011 and since then, has put in place several measures to encourage more supply of and demand for social investment, including establishing [Big Society Capital](#) as a 'wholesale' social investor (it provides funds to other investment intermediaries), trialling [social impact bonds](#) as a new form of financing designed to bring different types of investors into the market and promoting [community shares](#) as a way of crowdfunding investment for community projects. More recently, the UK government has launched a [matched crowdfunding](#) scheme for arts and heritage projects, in association with Nesta and Crowdfunder. Meanwhile, in [Portugal](#), the government has started to look at ways in which European Structural Funds can be used to support all stages of social innovations, including through grants, debt and equity investments.

2. SUPPORTIVE REGULATION AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

Socially innovative organisations often don't fit traditional institutional forms well, which can cause problems - for instance, not all social economy enterprises can access Horizon 2020 and COSME funding. In places like Estonia and [Ireland](#), social innovators have expressed a need to have legal frameworks that better meet their needs, and some national governments have already taken steps to do this. Examples of this include establishing the [Community Interest Company](#) (CIC) model in the UK, while in France the [Loi Economie sociale et solidaire](#) (ESS 2014) brought about a number of different commercial frameworks for social or solidarity-based businesses.

Regulation can stimulate or inhibit social innovation; for example around new forms of financing (like crowdfunding) and new business models being developed in collaborative economy initiatives. People in these sectors have called for 'smart regulation' that allows space for innovation while still protecting consumers and citizens. In the UK for example, the Financial Conduct Authority has created a '[regulatory sandbox](#)' to provide a 'safe space' for innovators to test out the impacts of new models without immediately incurring the usual regulatory requirements. Meanwhile, those in the digital social innovation community have called for a number of regulatory measures to encourage innovation, such as promotion of open access to research, open standards and interoperability (so that devices and services produced and delivered by different companies can communicate with one another).

3. OPENING UP PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PROCESSES

In Europe, public agencies are important potential 'customers' for social innovation. In their role as commissioners, funders and providers of public services, public agencies have the ability to help social innovators develop and test solutions, get them working and take them to scale. But this can only work if [procurement processes are open to social innovators of a variety of organisational forms](#) - small organizations or large, community sector, social economy as well as private sector or public organizations. One approach is to require social value to be considered as part of procurement decisions. In 2014, the EU published a [new public procurement directive](#) which asks public authorities to consider social value in their procurement decisions - member states were given until April 2016 to enact national legislation taking on these principles, although [by May 2016 most were still to do so](#). Amongst policy examples which make explicit use of social innovation principles, challenge-based procurement models, like the [Barcelona Open Challenge](#), are also gaining traction.

4. OPENING UP PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PROCESSES USING PUBLIC ASSETS IN SOCIALLY INNOVATIVE WAYS

Opening up access to public assets can stimulate social innovation. For example, the report [Policies for Shareable Cities](#) recommended that European policy makers should facilitate the sharing economy at a local level through interventions like allowing residents to lease residential parking spaces for shared

vehicles, designating lanes for ridesharing, creating incentives for urban farming on vacant or unused land, and facilitating the temporary use of empty commercial spaces. In Baltimore, USA, the Mayor created a [scheme](#) through which residents could apply to turn vacant housing lots into community spaces, amending planning regulations and working with utilities providers to help residents create parks, community gardens and a range of other non-commercial projects on otherwise unused land. Meanwhile, initiatives like Voidstarter in Ireland and SpareSpace in the Netherlands, which attempt to open up unused space to benefit young people and microentrepreneurs, present new opportunities for policymakers to partner with social innovators to address a number of local economic and regional development issues.

This doesn't just apply to physical, but also virtual assets. Digital social innovators have called for more opening up of public data to stimulate innovation - alongside measures to increase citizens' control of their own data.

5. RAISING AWARENESS AND BUILDING SKILLS

Policymakers can help to improve the legitimacy and visibility of social innovation through initiatives that map and measure activity, and attempt to measure its impact and contribution. The EC-funded Tepsie project, for example, set out a [blueprint for measuring social innovation](#), that would give national or regional policymakers a good evidence base to inform new policy measures. Meanwhile, other research has shown how awareness raising is also important within and between social innovation actors. For example, research on [crowdfunding for good causes](#) found that few voluntary and community organisations were aware of different crowdfunding models and how they could be used, and so recommended that policymakers and sector bodies promote training and resources that could help build capacity to use these new fundraising approaches.

WHAT NEXT?

Some parts of the social innovation community have engaged a lot with policymakers and have a good idea about how public policy could support them better. In other areas - for instance, where social innovation networks are less developed or formalised - there's been less work done to date. Through the Social Innovation Community project we're looking to reach out to social innovators across sectors and involve them in policy discussions. If you're interested in our work, we'd love to hear from you.

You can reach out to us on Twitter [@SICommunity_EU](#) using the hashtag #socinnpolicy or email us directly at policy@siceurope.eu

**SOCIAL
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Seven principles of socially innovative policymaking

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Seven principles of socially innovative policymaking

1. CHALLENGE-FOCUSED

Public authorities are tasked with dealing with some of the thorniest societal challenges we face: from climate change to poverty. Socially innovative policymaking seeks to find solutions for these complex challenges using collaborative, social innovation tools and approaches.

Challenge-led policy platforms: Barcelona City Council has partnered with Citymart to develop the Barcelona Open Challenge - a challenge-based platform which seeks to open up a range of city challenges prizes to entrepreneurs, social innovators and others. Winning solutions are contracted by the City Government through a process called challenge-based procurement. Past challenges have included:

- Reducing bicycle thefts in the city
- Empowering support systems to reduce social isolation
- Automatic detection and alerts of damaged road surfaces

2. OPENNESS

To effectively design and deliver better solutions, socially innovative policymaking needs to be open to new insights, new methods and approaches, and new forms of knowledge and expertise.

Crowdsourcing legislation: The principle of openness lies at the heart of initiatives like Finland's Open Ministry - a crowdsourcing campaign which successfully involved more than 250,000 Finns in co-writing and voting on citizen-led policy proposals, five of which have been put to a vote in the Finnish Parliament. Open Ministry founder, Joonas Pekkanen, founded the initiative as a way to enable a more deliberative democracy between citizens and their political representatives in the period following the 2008 financial crash.

3. HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN (HCD)

Policymaking is often developed in a public agency with an emphasis on administrative rather than user needs. HCD is a process which attempts to invert this logic, by having policymakers approach a policy challenge with 'professional empathy'. A number of methods and approaches support the use of HCD in

policy. User research, ethnographic methods, service safaris are just a few of the many tools available to policymakers.

Empathising to explore mobility policy solutions: The Slovakian city, Bratislava, set out to improve public transport access for disabled and handicapped persons. A team of people with disabilities, officials from municipality's transport department, students and lecturers of design and architecture from the Slovak Technical University and UNDP officials sought to personally immerse themselves in the experiences and emotional needs of users. After a design-thinking exercise, they returned to the office to capture and distil the insights gained and brainstormed on potential solutions.¹

4. COLLABORATION/CO-DESIGN

Socially innovative policymaking goes a step beyond consulting users and citizens to meaningfully involve them in the policy process. It is premised on the belief that policy solutions will be better if they incorporate the inputs and ideas provided by citizens and other stakeholders.

Working with 'citizen experts' to develop better policy solutions: Faced with an challenge of a diminished city budget, the City of Zeist, Netherlands decided to explore whether a collaborative citizen engagement strategy that tapped into the expertise, experience and skills of citizens could help find a solution to achieve budget savings to close its fiscal gap of EUR 6 million.

Over a three month period, two hundred 'citizen experts' explored new solutions related to a number of priority themes. The citizens were grouped based on their personal expertise. Importantly, the suggestions provided by these citizen experts were taken up by public officials involved. As a result of this targeted co-commissioning process, ninety-five per cent of all citizen proposals were adopted by the local council without changes.

5. EXPERIMENTATION AND EVIDENCE

Socially innovative policymaking is ultimately outcomes-focused, and seeks to identify whether a policy intervention is achieving its intended goal in a real-world setting. Designing experimental and evidence-informed policies enables policymakers to make better decisions, to monitor and evaluate what is working – and stop what isn't.

¹ Source: http://www.undp.org/content/dam/uspc/docs/GPCSE_Design%20Thinking.pdf

Designing experimental policy pilots: Policy programmes developed through big-bang approaches can present huge risks in terms of the financial and social costs. Socially innovative policies therefore aim to set up smaller scale experiments to test the outcomes of a policy intervention in a particular context, to learn from this, and to adapt the intervention accordingly. In 2017, universal basic income experiments will take place in a number of Dutch cities (Utrecht, Wageningen, Tilburg, Groningen and Nijmegen) and in Finland. These policy experiments aim to assess the viability of the interventions and the generate evidence on the outcomes they have in practice, before any changes (incremental or otherwise) are made to current welfare models.

6. ITERATION

Iteration - Socially innovative policies seek to adopt an agile approach to policy development where policy solutions are continually refined and revisited around a series of feedback loops. In this sense, an iterative policy development approach is at odds with traditional ‘waterfall’ or ‘big bang’ policy models - where a top-down policy strategy is devised and the policy solution is arrived at prescriptively.

Using an iterative approach to develop policy: The UK Government Digital Service and the Department for Work and Pensions (DWP) redesigned the Carer’s Allowance using an iterative approach. They released a beta version of the initiative more than year before the full launch, and adapted it based on feedback. The resulting policy initiative reported user satisfaction rates of around 90%.

7. CONNECTING AND SCALING

Scaling up of policy refers to the expansion, replication, adaptation and sustaining of effective policies, programmes or projects in geographic space and over time to reach a greater number of people. Ongoing policy scaling requires political support, and regular monitoring and evaluation to assess a policy continues to create impact as it grows. Embedding and sustaining change also requires creating synergies with other policies and programmes, while forging connections and alliances with others affected by or working on the policy challenge.

Scaling impact through social movements: The NHS’s [Five Year Forward View](#) strategy set out a plan to transform the NHS into a health and care social movement. Over a new three year period, the ‘Health as a Social Movement’ programme will set out to 1) Identify and develop exemplar social movements – creating real-world examples of communities mobilised for health and care 2) Demonstrate ‘what works’ – using rigorous evaluation approaches and 3) Support spread – enabling local areas to develop approaches that could be scaled or adapted and adopted in other communities.

Policy prompt sheet

Applying the seven principles of social innovation to policy

Social Innovation Community has developed a framework outlining how policy can both support social innovation and can be socially innovative in itself. Following on from our 'Seven principles of socially innovative policymaking', this prompt sheet is intended to support policymakers to apply these principles to current policy challenges.

1 Challenge-focused

Public authorities are tasked with dealing with some of the thorniest societal challenges we face: from climate change to poverty. Socially innovative policymaking seeks to find solutions for these complex challenges using collaborative, social innovation tools and approaches.

- Have you thought about who is affected by this challenge?
- Is there anyone else's perspectives you should consider to help reframe the challenge?
- Have you taken steps to fully understand the context of this challenge? For instance, have you taken steps to explore whether this challenge is a symptom of a broader more entrenched issue?
- Have you looked to identify and draw on other examples of policy approaches that have tackled similar challenges - nationally or internationally?
- Have you planned the key parts of the challenge you would like the policy solution to address?

2 Openness

To effectively design and deliver better solutions, socially innovative policymaking needs to be open to new insights, new methods and approaches, and new forms of knowledge and expertise.

- Could you design your policy approach so that taps into the experience and/or expertise of citizens, social innovators and other stakeholders?
- Could you use crowdsourcing or citizensourcing to help gain new insights on the public's ideas or suggestions on this policy topic?
- Could you use citizen reporting to deepen awareness on a policy issue? (For instance, using social media to live report environmental data or transport issues)
- Would problem-based procurement or other open social innovation methods be an appropriate approach to help drive ideation and identify possible policy solutions?

3 Human-Centered Design (HCD)

Public authorities are tasked with dealing with policymaking. Policymaking is often developed in a public agency with an emphasis on administrative rather than user needs. HCD is a process which attempts to invert this logic, by having policymakers approach a policy challenge with 'professional empathy'. A number of methods and approaches support the use of HCD in policy. User research, ethnographic methods, service safaris are just a few of the many tools available to policymakers.

- Have you done a network map of actors and users to identify the key actors and unusual suspects who are impacted by this policy? (Your map should include actors from government, civil society, the advocacy and lobby sector, social innovation practitioners and users)
- Have you considered how the policy solution will meet the needs of target users' (including unusual suspects such as remote communities)? (Methods to do this include user research, user personas, service mapping and service safaris)

4 Collaboration/co-design

Socially innovative policymaking goes a step beyond consulting users and citizens to meaningfully involve them in the policy process. It is premised on the belief that policy solutions will be better if they incorporate the inputs and ideas provided by citizens and other stakeholders.

- Have you considered what the anticipated outcomes of this policy approach should or might be?
- Have you considered how you could design a policy pilot in order to assess whether your policy approach is having its intended outcomes?
- Does your organisation already have the skills and know-how to design and evaluate an experimental policy approach? If not, have you considered other options (e.g. a research partnership with universities)?
- Have you considered what you will do if evaluations show the policy approach does not achieve the intended outcomes?

5 Experimentation and evidence

Socially innovative policymaking is ultimately outcomes-focused, and seeks to identify whether a policy intervention is achieving its intended goal in a real-world setting. Designing experimental and evidence-informed policies enables policymakers to make better decisions, to monitor and evaluate what is working, and stop what isn't.

- Have you considered what the anticipated outcomes of this policy approach should or might be?
- Have you considered how you could design a policy pilot in order to assess whether your policy approach is having its intended outcomes?
- Does your organisation already have the skills and know-how to design and evaluate an experimental policy approach? If not, have you considered other options (e.g. a research partnership with universities)?
- Have you considered what you will do if evaluations show the policy approach does not achieve the intended outcomes?

6 Iteration

Socially innovative policies seek to adopt an agile approach to policy development where policy solutions are continually refined and revisited around a series of feedback loops. In this sense, an iterative policy development approach is at odds with the traditional 'waterfall' or 'big bang' policy models - where a top-down policy strategy is devised and the policy solution is arrived at prescriptively

- In what ways could you phase the roll-out of your policy approach so that it can be refined, improved and scaled over time?
- Have you designed your policy approach so that there are opportunities for feedback to occur at key points in the policy process?
- Would it be appropriate for you to use policy sprints when developing your policy approach?
- Are there tools you could use to gain insights of user satisfaction with the programme or service?
- Have measures been taken to ensure that stakeholder/user feedback and suggestions are acted upon properly?
- Have you taken steps to plan in flexibility to your policy approach so that it responds to user research and other insights that emerge as the policy process develops?

7 Connecting/scaling

Scaling up of policy refers the expansion, replication, adaptation and sustaining of effective policies, programmes or projects in geographic space and over time to reach a greater number of people. Ongoing policy scaling requires political support, and regular monitoring and evaluation to assess a policy is still creating impact as it grows. Embedding and sustaining change also requires creating synergies with other policies and programmes, while forging connections and alliances with others affected by or working on the policy challenge.

- Have you taken adequate measures to assess whether your policy approach works?
- Have you identified relevant partners inside and outside government who can support with implementation of the policy solution?
- Have you planned for budgets and considered how your policy will fare in the event of legal and administrative changes?
- Are there ways that you could plan to build a social movement around this policy solution? Have you consider what actors would you involve and what role they might play in sustaining your policy solution?
- Could you support others looking to address similar policy challenges elsewhere - either nationally or internationally - by packaging your learnings into policy playbooks and guides?

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Regional case study: Community Lab, Emilia Romagna

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Community Lab, Emilia Romagna Region: Using openness and collaboration to better respond to complex social challenges

1. BACKGROUND

Community Lab is a public policy initiative based in the region of Emilia Romagna, Italy. It sets out to improve community wellbeing by encouraging community empowerment and engagement with the policy development process. The initiative is led by the Emilia Romagna Regional Health and Social Agency, and Lab activities are carried out in collaboration with local government agencies and others.

2. DEFINING PUBLIC CHALLENGES THROUGH OPENNESS AND COLLABORATION

Community Lab sets out to open up how social and health problems are framed by integrating the perspectives of citizens, marginalized groups, such as migrants or precarious workers – as well as social economy actors and other stakeholders – into the policy planning process. In doing this, Community Lab transforms seemingly isolated policy challenges into collective and shared objectives of a participative programme.

Working collaboratively in this way also enables Community Lab to go beyond traditional policy targets and embrace the more cross-cutting dimensions and complex realities of social problems. The role of public authorities is changed in this arrangement: with public bodies, private, active citizenship and enterprises all taking on a more active role in co-creating and co-managing new policy solutions. Furthermore, human-centred design principles and systems thinking are used to build up the innovation capacity of the government agencies involved – by uncovering opportunities to redesign policy strategy and services in a way that is more in line with real user need at a micro level; and at a macro level – radically rethinking how complex problems are framed and approached.

3. AN EXPERIMENTAL, ITERATIVE APPROACH TO POLICYMAKING

The Lab uses a method which seeks to put local place-based experiments and action-based learning at the heart of the public sector. The Lab's methodology starts out with a regional call to identify the most effective local social innovation solutions/initiatives operating in the health and social welfare sector – which are referred to as 'case studies'. Emilia Romagna local communities and municipalities then submit case studies outlining their relevant local social innovation examples. Typically these local initiatives are promoted by the local municipalities, or are bottom-up initiatives that had already garnered attention from policymakers.

These 'case studies' are then analysed to assess their effectiveness and scalability, and the analysis helps inform the design of a series local pilot experiments intended to tackle a number of different health and social sector challenges. Emilia Romagna regional officers then select the most effective examples to be adopted on an experimental basis by the community labs.

The local pilot experiments are then tested, and where they are shown to be effective in practice, efforts are made to replicate them in new contexts. Past experiments have sought to tackle challenges ranging from topics such as testing innovative participative practices for health and social wellbeing; trialling participatory planning, tackling gender-related issues, and encouraging welfare innovations.

Three sets of experiments have been run as part of Community Lab's three editions, and were run in 2013, 2014 and 2015. Each of these iterations has shown a consistent commitment to refining and iterating the method. For instance, the 2013 Lab edition sought to trial the participatory planning approach; the 2014 edition then sought to identify an evaluation framework to capture the outcomes of this approach, and the 2015 edition focused on improving the architecture that would facilitate the scaling of the Lab methodology into new contexts: assessing the replicability of the method in other institutional processes (scaling up the process from local contexts to Municipality Unions, to Metropolitan cities) and modifying the guidelines so that they could be adopted in new areas.

4. CONNECTING AND SCALING

After the first edition, the Emilia Romagna region found the Community Lab could be an effective mechanism to promote social involvement and social innovation in the Region. Replicating and testing the method in new contexts and with the involvement of new actors was supported by empirical guidelines and a practitioner's toolbox for each of the different policy experiments. Each edition of Community Lab provided a contextually-specific response, but the collection and the analysis of each of the experiments allowed for the drawing up of effective measures to empower the Social and Health

Regional and Local Services to achieve a participatory approach to better meet citizens' needs. Since 2012 the Community Lab method has been used to develop the region's health and social wellbeing plan, and the approach is currently being experimented with to develop regional plans in other sectors, such as housing and urban regeneration.

5. LESSONS LEARNED

Local policymakers and public officials are the main beneficiaries of the Community Lab programme. The Lab is understood (after the first set of experiments in 2013) as an effective training method to foster social innovation in the Public Administration's different sectors, to produce greater understanding of public challenges and how to solve them through the action of the community, starting from experimental initiatives and collective processes. Community Lab has resulted in the creation of a community of practice based on the inductive learning (starting with the initial identification and analysis of local challenges) and the growth of a new culture and new ways of planning based on the integration between different areas and sectors.

**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

Regional case study: La 27e Région, France

Sophie Reynolds, Nesta

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693883.

La 27e Région works with policymakers to create a culture that supports social innovation in French regional government

1. BACKGROUND

La 27e Région is a government innovation lab based in France which conducts action-research programmes that support civil servants to try out new socially innovative approaches to public policymaking, particularly at a regional level. The initiative was first founded in 2008 by a group comprised of presidents from French regional governments, former civil servants and consultants, who together set out to address the shortcomings in how traditional public policy is designed and delivered. The initiative resulted in an alliance with the Association of French Regions (ARF) in 2008, and subsequently grew to encompass other levels of public authorities, including those operating at a national level. In 2012, La 27e Région was spun out to become an independent not-for-profit organisation.

2. BUILDING THE SOCIAL INNOVATION CAPABILITIES OF POLICYMAKERS

La 27e Région's mission is to create a public sector culture that supports social innovation through the co-creation and co-design of public policies involving citizens through user-driven models. To achieve this mission, La 27e Région's multi-disciplinary team - made up of ethnographers, sociologists, designers and others - run two kinds of practical capacity-building programmes for policymakers: [Territoires en résidence](#) and [la Transfo](#). These programmes are designed to encourage policymakers to rethink public policy processes by applying a range of tools and methods that are underpinned by human-centred design, openness, collaboration and experimentalism.

3. ITERATING POLICY SUPPORT PROGRAMMES

[Territoires en résidence](#) (*The Residencies*) was the first of La 27e Région's capacity-building programmes for policymakers. For three weeks out of the programme's six month duration, La 27e

Région's team is deployed to support policymakers to explore new policy projects where they can gain exposure to ethnographic and other socially innovative methods. While *The Residencies* were useful at exposing policymakers to the basic methods and principles needed to make more socially innovative policy, the policymakers still relied very much on the expertise and guidance of La 27e Région's team to drive the innovation process.

What then followed was a second programme called la Transfo (*The Transformation*) - which aimed to build on the learnings of *The Residencies*. It had two key objectives: 1) inspire civil servants to develop a 'professional curiosity' to tackle policy challenges in socially innovative ways and build up their capabilities and skills to do this effectively and 2) develop new innovation teams within regional government, who beyond the programme could sustain the innovation effort from within the public institution setting.

The Transformation differed from *The Residencies* in that it took place over a longer two year period, during which 15 civil servants were supported by a design team. This time, La 27e Région's designers were involved throughout the process to ensure the projects were user-led and adhered to social innovation policy principles. Civil servants started the programme with a test case - which involved a combination of group sessions and meetings with key stakeholders. Over the course of the programme, the focus then shifted onto priority policy challenges facing the regional government. By the second month, participants were expected to be able to prototype and test policy ideas themselves, and make use of a range of tools such as user personas and service models.

4. IMPACTS OF LA TRANSFO

Of all the policy ideas generated as part of the La Transfo programme, 50% were successfully implemented by regional government. A good example of such a policy solution is Hub PME (SME Hub) which set out to significantly simplify the application process for small-medium sized businesses looking for support from the Regional Council.

The initial group of civil servants who first participated in La Transfo have gone on to create their own innovation team housed at regional government. La Transfo has also been instrumental in creating a community of socially innovative policymakers, a number which has grown from the initial fifteen civil servants who participated, to a network of 70. This marks a significant growth in the number of policymakers using social innovation approaches (particularly human-centred approaches) in their work.

Ongoing sharing of skills and knowledge is facilitated between different government agencies by 'Intertransfos' - retreats and exchanges that bring together policymakers and teams involved in the programme and communities involved in similar efforts together every six months. The meetings are

hosted either in Pays de la Loire or one of the three other regions that participated in La Transfo (Bourgogne, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, Champagne-Ardenne). There, participants exchange and discuss each other's successes and challenges.

5. ITERATION AND GROWTH

In the two years since La Transfo's initial pilot, La 27e Région is once again in the process of rolling out a new phase of the programme. This time it will engage ten new public authorities in the process (including city halls, sub-regional authorities, regional entities, major public authorities). This phase of the programme is being adapted based on the lessons learned since its first iteration. Further adjustments have been made so that the programme better meets the requirements of this new cohort of public organisations who are set to get involved. For instance, the duration of the experiment has been shortened to reduce costs for the participating public authorities and the Intertransfos component of the programme has been strengthened to encourage greater opportunities for inter-agency exchanges - which it is hoped will lead to more public sector innovation at a grander scale.

**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

Regional case study: e-Estonia

Sophie Reynolds, Nesta

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693883.

e-Estonia: how Estonia's national digital strategy could open up more opportunities for digital social innovation in the region

1. BACKGROUND

At the point of its independence in 1991, less than half of Estonia's population had a telephone line. What followed was a remarkable relaunch of the country through the pioneering use of digital technologies. Without being burdened by legacy systems, the small country was able to leapfrog into the digital age - choosing, for instance, to upgrade old analogue phone system with digital ones. The use of ICT solutions to facilitate dialogue between the government and citizens began early on in that process. Early examples of initiatives included the TOM (Today I Decide) system developed in 2001, which enabled citizens to submit policy proposals, the introduction of e-voting in 2005 - through the use of an ID-card based system - that allowed citizens to vote online in local, national and European Union elections and the osale.ee platform in 2007. This enabled public consultations with individuals and interest groups to inform draft policy documents.

2. AN ENABLING ENVIRONMENT FOR DIGITAL SOCIAL INNOVATION

e-Estonia - a key mechanism to drive Estonia's Digital Strategy 2020 - illustrates Estonia's ongoing and optimistic embrace of digital technologies, and has laid the foundation for a supportive digital social innovation environment. Estonia's Digital Agenda 2020 ultimately seeks to support the use of ICT to help Estonia achieve three core objectives: 1) economic competitiveness, 2) the well-being of people and 3) the efficiency of public administration.

Led by the government, e-Estonia supports the creation of electronic solutions that can facilitate online citizen interaction with the State - and has resulted in specific e-services, such as I-voting and E-ID. "E-ID" is an online verification system that allows citizens to access the state portal. It functions as a one-stop-shop of government e-services ranging from public healthcare to education. The data from all these e-services is linked by an interoperability platform called X-Road, which makes safe and secure information collection and exchange possible between different public offices with a handful of clicks.

Examples of e-services include:

- e-services for citizens e.g. citizen engagement and e-voting;
- E-services in health care e.g. online prescriptions and health records;
- E-services in education e.g. e-school;

e-Estonia is underpinned by a number of principles which are broadly in line with those of digital social innovation:

- 01 Decentralisation.** e-Estonia has no central database, and every stakeholder, be it a government department, a ministry or a business, gets to choose its own system in its own time.
- 02 Interconnectivity.** All the elements in the system have to be able to work together smoothly.
- 03 Open platform.** Any institution can use the public key infrastructure.
- 04 Open-ended process.** e-Estonia acts as a continuous project to keep growing and improving organically.
- 05 Respecting citizens' data privacy.** Estonia has set out to use smart solutions to ensure that people have control over the privacy of their lives and data. Recognising the need for technological products and platforms that are “private by design” has created greater public trust in Estonia's e-government initiatives.

3. OPPORTUNITIES TO MAKE THE DIGITAL SOCIETY VISION MORE SOCIAL

Estonia's effort to develop and use e-services has been accompanied by a concerted campaign to ensure all citizens have access to the internet — in 2011, fixed broadband coverage in Estonia was at 93.9%. And Estonia's Broadband Infrastructure Network (EstWIN) has focused on rolling out fast broadband to regions where it had been previously unavailable, allowing for future applications such as telemedicine or online learning. Estonia's president, Toomas Hendrik Ilves, credits the success of Estonia's Digital Society vision as not so much about ditching legacy technology as shedding “legacy thinking”. The country has wholly embraced this “no legacy principle”: no important ICT solutions older than 13 years are permitted in the public sector to ensure public services remain up-to-date with emerging technologies.

“The country's success in pioneering e-services and online citizen engagement could open opportunities for Estonia's public sector to make greater use of socially innovative policymaking approaches...”

This success in pioneering e-services and online citizen engagement could open opportunities for Estonia's public sector to make greater use of socially innovative policymaking approaches to address some of the country's most complex challenges – an area that the government has not yet fully

explored. The Estonian Civil Society Development Concept (EKAK) and the Digital Strategy 2020 set out an intention to create more formalised partnerships between the public sector and civil society. However, few Estonian policies so far explicitly acknowledge or set out to support social innovation. Furthermore, the digital social innovation community seems surprisingly underdeveloped - as of mid-2016, no Estonian organisations or projects existed on the digitalsocial.eu map. Although efforts have been taken to introduce Social Impact Bonds in the Estonian setting, some local stakeholders argue that Estonia needs to create a more supportive environment for the various kinds of organisations that seek to create social impact - whether they do this using tech-enabled methods or simply work alongside others who do. Jaan Aps, chairman of the management board of ESEN (Estonian Social Enterprise Network), has noted a need for legislative modifications to support socially-oriented organisations, to remove unfair (and/or misguided) barriers to support (especially in relation to ineligibility of civil society organisations to business support) and to promote consideration of social and environmental impact in public procurement. However, Aps has added, “the prerequisite for both of those developments is better understanding of the concept of societal impact by public sector decision makers.”

**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

Mobilearn – the digital platform supporting migrant integration

Sophie Reynolds, Nesta

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693883.

Mobilearn – the digital platform supporting migrant integration

Mobilearn is a mobile-based service that provides newly arrived immigrants with important information in an easy and accessible way. As part of the Social Innovation Community project, Sophie Reynolds interviewed Ernest Radal, founder of Mobilearn to speak about the platform’s biggest successes and to learn about the value of working with government to achieve greater impact.

SOPHIE REYNOLDS: EUROPE IS FACING UNPRECEDENTED CHALLENGES WITH MIGRATION. IN WHAT WAYS HAS MOBILEARN BEEN ABLE TO SUPPORT PUBLIC AGENCIES TO BETTER DEAL WITH NEWLY ARRIVED MIGRANTS, AND WHAT HAVE BEEN THE BIGGEST IMPACTS TO DATE?

Ernest Radal: “Europe is facing perhaps its biggest challenge ever - the great wave of immigration that we have seen in recent years. Immigration isn’t just going to stop, and we therefore need to create new, smart, digital tools that empower people and allow for faster, more efficient integration.

We need to reduce the human handling of administrators, offer asylum-seekers early and meaningful access to employment from the very first day, and ensure that unnecessary waiting time is converted into time to better equip new arrivals with the kind of support they need to adjust to the society they’re entering into.

This is all done in Mobilearn, by providing community and civic information in different languages, offering an immediate access to the labour market, mapping competency and experiences faster, providing the tools for language learning, and providing housing options.

Mobilearn sets out to create a “one-stop-shop” platform for immigrants. By distributing Mobilearn, the

public agencies have noticed that the immigrants they encounter have become more independent, language learning has occurred faster, and questions and answers to civic information are found more independently by the immigrant him or herself. They've gotten to grips with their new home faster. By adding some of their personal details to the Mobilearn, they've also been able to create CVs/resumes and apply for jobs immediately from day one. The platform is certified by the Swedish Data Protection Authority – which ensures that we meet data privacy standards in accordance with EU laws. Immigrants, the end-users, are in complete control and have to approve any requests to access their data.

In addition to aiding faster integration, the public agencies have found themselves saving time that is easily converted to real economical savings. Since being set up, Mobilearn partnerships have made key services available to tens of thousands of immigrants, with a potential saving of €421 per end user a year, on average for our clients.

Two users of the Mobilearn platform at Kinda Municipality, Sweden

SR: MOBILEARN HAS HAD CONSIDERABLE SUCCESS IN SWEDEN, PARTNERING WITH APPROXIMATELY HALF OF ALL SWEDEN'S MUNICIPALITIES, REGIONS AND COUNTY GOVERNMENTS, AND THE SWEDISH MIGRATION AND LABOUR OFFICE. SR: SR: HOW DID YOU FIRST WORK TO CREATE THESE PARTNERSHIPS, AND WHAT HAVE BEEN THE KEYS INSIGHTS YOU WOULD SHARE WITH OTHER SOCIAL INNOVATORS LOOKING TO WORK WITH GOVERNMENT PARTNERS IN THIS WAY?

ER: "Well, first and foremost we realised early on that we needed to partner with the municipalities and county governments for maximal impact. Often when you meet social entrepreneurs or social innovators they don't recognise that to scale in the social impact sector, long and sustainable partnerships with public sector can be crucial. Also during our early development we created an advisory board, consisting of representatives of, among others, two of Sweden's largest municipalities. That way they gave us input on the product, as potential future clients.

"...to scale in the social impact sector, long and sustainable partnerships with public sector can be crucial."

Secondly, we decided to start offering our service to the market as soon as we had a 'minimum viable product', meaning we released version one, and then continued to develop and expand the service as we went along. For economical sustainability this means everything to an early-stage startup just about to launch. The experience in developing Mobilearn has really taught me the value of not waiting too long. Work to put what you've got out there faster.

As far as first contact is concerned there is no magic formula, we did what any other sales organisation would do – e.g. cold calls, and setting up meetings.

Some key insights from this experience would be:

- 01** Involve potential partners at an early stage, make them key stakeholders in your development.
- 02** Create a roadmap, share it with your partners, and then show them how you're making progress towards achieving those key milestones. This will signal you are a partner that keeps your promises and delivers, which will help you in the future.
- 03** Consider engaging with stake-holders in a bottom-up way - not only top-down. You need to involve people on the ground. We didn't just meet with senior ministers, city mayors and heads of units. We also met social workers and interpreters. Understanding their needs was crucial to gaining the buy-in of management of these frontline services.
- 04** Have a sustainable business model - your partners need to understand that you're not suddenly going to disappear. Insufficient economical sustainability is often the main obstacle for the public sector collaborating with / buying from you

as an innovator.

- 05** Offer support - your local government or municipality has probably never done anything like this before. Make sure they feel safe and understand you're going to "hold their hand" throughout the process.
- 06** Articulate what the results of working with you will be - then make sure you can demonstrate the success metrics you initially decided upon
- 07** Find a way of measuring your social impact - and then convert it to economic impact.
- 08** Last and certainly not least – social innovators and entrepreneurs can be afraid to sell to government. The commissioners and public officials you're working with are human, and will respond to a well-communicated, well-developed product or service that can support what they do – regardless of whether they're positioned in government or not.

A client tries the Mobilearn platform.

SR: RECENTLY, STOCKHOLM UNIVERSITY DID AN INDEPENDENT RESEARCH STUDY IN ORDER TO EVALUATE MOBILEARN'S IMPACT. CAN YOU TELL US ABOUT YOUR OWN JOURNEY WORKING TO MEASURE MOBILEARN'S IMPACT, AND HOW YOU WORKED TO DEVELOP AND ACCESS THE SKILLS AND TOOLS (BOTH WITHIN YOUR ORGANISATION AND BEYOND) NEEDED TO DO THIS?

ER: "The Gordian knot of all social innovation is how to measure the actual impact. Now, all social innovators and entrepreneurs have different stakeholders, whether they know it or not, and all these stakeholders have different needs and expectations. As a social entrepreneur you need to identify all stakeholders and then determine "what's in it for them". For the social worker, maybe it's about the immigrant's ability to integrate, for the mayor of the local municipality maybe it's about how much taxpayers' money he or she is saving.

There is no magical formula to creating models for measurement of social impact or social-economical return of investment. You have to invent it yourself in your sector and make sure it's statistically viable, and can be made standard across all your activities.

The University of Stockholm decided to evaluate and measure the impact of immigrants' access to open data and what effect it had on the municipalities and the society as a whole. For the purpose of their research study they chose the Mobilearn application, and measured a municipality that had distributed Mobilearn to immigrants, comparing it to a municipality that had not.

The University of Stockholm concluded that every municipality had an average of 13 different stakeholders. These included, for example, pre-schools, police and healthcare providers. They then monitored these different stakeholders and after a year got an exact number on the actual time saved, and then finally depending on salaries and external cost etc., also on cost savings in total per end user of the platform.

We captured end users' feedback through SMS surveys, and measured the actual usage of the Mobilearn service, looking at statistics and analysing the end users' data. But we also needed to convert the social impact into social-economical (or 'hard') impact.

We managed to do this by creating the "Mobilearn model" – a 24 month activity plan based on our clients' different KPIs (key performance indicators). The client commits to following this plan, by distributing, working with and including Mobilearn in their plan – in order to reach agreed upon goals during the two years, or else, we can't guarantee success. On top of that, we then add the economical savings as calculated by the Stockholm University, thus creating a total potential saving, actual savings or loss of money/investment.

As a direct result of this we also had to create two different roles within the company: a customer care role and an education officer. The local municipality, governments (etc.) get certified and educated by

our education officer and then our customer care support ensures that the clients feel safe, secure and has access to statistics, plans and numbers throughout their entire plan.

SR: HAS WORKING CLOSELY WITH PUBLIC SECTOR AGENCIES IMPACTED YOUR OWN WORK, AND HAS IT BENEFITTED YOUR VENTURE IN ANY WAY?

ER: “All new experiences make you develop and become better, stronger and wiser. We have had a unique opportunity to work with public sector agencies and during the years we’ve had to adopt and improve in order to create a common path forward together with governments. We have become more patient, learned to adjust to structures in a more open way and also learned a lot about how public procurement works.

It has also changed our organisation positively in that sense that it’s demanded us to focus on improving our structure, our long-term thinking and the way we deliver client support within the company – all of which have strengthened our offer and deepened our impact.

SR: IN YOUR EXPERIENCE, DOES POLICY (E.G. PUBLIC COMMISSIONING, REGULATION) ENABLE THESE SORTS OF PARTNERSHIPS BETWEEN SOCIAL INNOVATORS AND GOVERNMENT? IN WHAT WAYS IS POLICY ENABLING/LIMITING WORKING IN THIS WAY?

ER: “Unfortunately I can’t say that current policy really supports this kind of working. The challenge with social innovations targeting the public sector is that it takes a very long time, more than average time in private sector, to be successful. The risk is disproportionately on the social innovator. If you try to approach private equity or even social impact investors they will quickly turn you down, since it’s high risk to invent, sell and then implement a public sector product or service. Effectively working in this way in the future is going to mean sharing the risk between public sector and social innovators and it would be great to find a common model that would enable rapid evaluation.

Ernest Radal was a juror of the [2016 European Social Innovation Competition](#). The 2016 competition focuses on social innovation for refugees and migrants.

Images courtesy of Ernest Radal, Mobilelearn